

Determining the optimal cabin insulator: Examination of odour, sound absorption behaviour, cost, and formability characteristics of ten felt composites

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ABSTRACT

The paper has composed in order to identify the optimal felt composite for cabin insulator among 10 different felt composites which are derived from various proportions of cotton, jute, and recycled denim fibres. These felt composites have been scrutinised in perspective of four criteria, as odour factor, sound absorption coefficient (SAC) factor, cost factor, formability factor. While industrial standards have been applied to cost assignment, paper has employed unique methodologies for odour, SAC, and formability. Odour analysis involved precise examination of VDA 270 Variant B standard test results using power mean. For SAC, it has developed a bespoke method using ISO 10534-2 tests and a Python code for sound absorption behaviour analysis within specific frequency ranges. The determining of the formability factor has been made with an ingenuine method that based on structured sectoral experience. These innovative and ingenuine approaches are expected to enrich scientific literature and inspire future research. Furthermore, the integrated AHP-PROMETHEE methods emphasised the logical selection process for the optimal composite, particularly remarkable for NVH product development. Thus, this paper calls intellectuals and researchers to evaluate these new approaches.

Keywords: Felt composite; Odour; Sound absorption coefficient (SAC); Formability; Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Fibres are cylindric chemical substances that is longer in length than in width, which might be produced naturally and artificially [1]. Natural fibres might be produced by animals and plants or might be occurred as a result of geologic incidents [1].

Artificial fibres might be synthesised by chemical and physical processing of some polymers, which are not eager to fiberized as of their natura.

Despite fibres can be used directly in a lot of industry, in automotive industry they are mostly functionate as the raw material of felts. Felts are composite chemical substances that has been obtained from fibres after several chemical and physical treatment. Thanks to their fibrous structure, felts are convenient chemical

substances for absorption of high-frequency noise and damping of high-frequency vibration [2] [3]. As a NVH product, felts might be utilised for sound absorption directly as sound insulator. Felt composites' evaluation criteria are differentiate correspondingly to their various utilisations. Common criteria for felt composites in NVH sector are sound absorption coefficient (SAC) factor, formability factor, mildew factor, flammability factor, odour factor, fogging factor, abrasion factor. Flammability is a mandatory test for felt composites in automotive industry and, it is commonly carried out with the perspective of UL-94 standard. The fogging test is the other mandatory test that has been carried out to determine the amount of chemical release of the felt composite under certain ambient conditions. In spite of there are a plenty of fogging test standard, it is

mostly carried out in standard of SAE-J-1756 or, ISO-6452 or, DIN-75201.

The paper aims to select the optimal felt composite among ten composites that has been produced to utilise as cabin insulator, within the evaluation of their sectoral utilisation in perspective of four discrete criteria: Odour, SAC, cost, formability. These ten felt composites have been synthesised fundamentally with the various compositions of recycled denim fibre, cotton fibre, jute fibre, and phenolic resin. Mandatory tests have been carried out with convenient standards and all of these ten felt composites has successfully passed flammability test and fogging test. Nevertheless, the detailed information about these tests have not been shared in this paper due to its special constitute of know-how.

II. METHOD AND MATERIAL

2.1. Odour Test

The odour test was carried out according to variant B of the VDA 270 standard and the test setup was created as required by this standard. Within the scope of this setup, 60 ± 6 grams samples of each felt composition were prepared. These samples were then placed in a 3 litres test container with a beaker containing 150 mL of pure water. They were then acclimatized at 23 ± 2 °C for 24 ± 1 hour. The tested compositions were evaluated by three different experts on a scale of 1 to 6 according to the standard. The odour factor of the felt composites was determined by power mean over the results. The exponent in power mean has been accepted as 4 to emphasise the higher values of odour among three evaluations. Keeping the sample under certain temperature and humidity conditions for a certain period of time aims to simulate typical conditions of use of the material. In the odour evaluation phase, the odour emitted is examined and evaluated against a specific standard. Finally, the test results are reported and interpreted. Odour is a minimization-directed criterion because of lower values are more preferable.

Table 1: Odour grade scale according to VDA 270 Variant B

Odour grade	Meanings
Grade 1	Not perceptible
Grade 2	Perceptible, not disturbing
Grade 3	Clearly perceptible, but not disturbing
Grade 4	Disturbing
Grade 5	Strongly disturbing
Grade 6	Not acceptable

2.2. Impedance Tube Test

SAC value measurement with impedance tube was performed according to ISO 10534-2 standard with utilisation of Brüel & Kjær methodology. In experiment mechanism, there are an impedance tube which met the expectations of Brüel & Kjær methodology, two size of samples for each individual felt composites that one of them has been cut into 30 mm in diameter and the other one has been cut into 100 mm in diameter. Measurements have been carried out in medium which is 23 °C and 50 % of relative humidity, according to test standard. Afterwards, the average SAC values of felt composites in subjected frequency interval which means the SA (sound absorption) behaviour of felt composites has been calculated within Equation 1. In this calculation, a and b values that Equation 1 contains has been detected within a code that performs logarithmic regression, which has been compiled by Python software language within the utilisation of NumPy, Matplotlib, and SciPy libraries. The f value that Equation 1 contains, represents the subjected frequency interval, and it has been accepted as the difference between higher frequency and lower frequency. These values are representing the SAC factor for each felt composites. SAC is a maximization-directed criterion because of higher values are more preferable.

$$\text{Average SAC} = a + \log(f) + b \quad (1)$$

2.3. Cost Assignment

Fundamental mathematical calculations have been used while cost factor was calculating. Initially, the unit prices of each fibre type and phenolic resin has been detected as Euro (€). Afterwards, the costs of felt composites has been calculated according to fibre and resin usage for each individual. Overall costs of felt composites represents cost factor of them. Cost is a minimization-directed criterion because of lower values are more preferable.

2.4. Formability Assignment

Formability is a crucial factor felt composites that are used in mass production systems. Formability expresses the forming ability of the felt composites in certain temperature and pressure conditions, and it is not contingent upon any standards. It is usually determined by subjective evaluations based on expert opinions or sectoral experience. In this study, formability has been determined by resin usage in felt composites. At this point it is a key know-how that how resin functionate in felt composites. Resin compounds are mostly utilised in felt composites

manufacturing processes to enhance the structure's formability. Hence, when less formable felt composites are in question, the more resin usage is needed. In this paper, formability factor has been accepted as the resin amount that was used to form felt composites, individually. Formability is a minimization-directed criterion because of lower values are more preferable.

2.5. AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process)

AHP structured within the academic and scientific literature's instructions [4]. Initially, criteria evaluation has been made by two experts based on Saaty scale. The results of these evaluations has been synthesised in a pair-wise comparison matrix. Then, pair-wise comparison matrix has been normalized by Equation 2. Equation 2 expresses normalization formula of the pair-wise comparison matrix, where C_{ij} means element of the comparison matrix, x_{ij} means element of the normalized comparison matrix, and $i = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, m\}$. Then Eigenvector has been obtained from normalized pairwise comparison matrix. Afterwards, D matrix has been formed for obtaining the CI (consistency index). Then RI (random index) has been obtained from Table 2. Finally, CR (consistency ratio) has been calculated, referring the Equation 3.

$$x_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^m C_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

Table 2: Random consistency index values

Matrix size	Random consistency index
1	0,00
2	0,00
3	0,58
4	0,90

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (3)$$

2.6. PROMETHEE (Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation)

PROMETHEE implementation has been structured onto Eigenvector from AHP has been determined. Method has two main septs to outrank the decision points, PROMETHEE I (partial ranking) and PROMETHEE II (complete ranking) [5]. The preference functions has been determined for each criteria based on common preference function that are in use for PROMETHEE methodology [6]. Afterwards, global preference indexes has been calculated for each individual felt composites according to their criterion directions.

Global preference index values has been utilised to detect positive and negative preference flow values within the Equation 4 and Equation 5 respectively, where n means the number of decision points, A means a decision point, x means a decision point other than A, and π means global preference index. Positive and negative preference flow values has been evaluated based on PROMETHEE logic that has been shared in Table 3. Within the results of these evaluation, PROMETHEE I (partial ranking) has been formed. Finally, Equation 6 has been used to determine the net flow score of each felt composite to form PROMETHEE II (complete ranking).

$$\varphi^+ = \frac{\sum \pi(A,x)}{n-1} \quad (4)$$

$$\varphi^- = \frac{\sum \pi(x,A)}{n-1} \quad (5)$$

Table 3: PROMETHEE I logic set

Implication	Situation
$\Phi^+(A) > \Phi^+(B)$ and $\Phi^-(A) < \Phi^-(B)$	A is dominant to B
$\Phi^+(A) > \Phi^+(B)$ and $\Phi^-(A) = \Phi^-(B)$	A is dominant to B
$\Phi^+(A) = \Phi^+(B)$ and $\Phi^-(A) < \Phi^-(B)$	A is dominant to B
$\Phi^+(A) = \Phi^+(B)$ and $\Phi^-(A) = \Phi^-(B)$	A and B are indifferent
$\Phi^+(A) > \Phi^+(B)$ and $\Phi^-(A) > \Phi^-(B)$	A and B are incomparable
$\Phi^+(A) < \Phi^+(B)$ and $\Phi^-(A) < \Phi^-(B)$	A and B are incomparable

$$\varphi(A) = \varphi(A)^+ - \varphi(A)^- \quad (6)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Odour Factor

The results of odour test that has been carried out according to VDA 270 Variant B standard and processed as aforementioned in previous chapter has been shared in Table 4.

Table 4: Odour factor assessments

Felt composite	Odour factor
K1	2,4774
K2	1,5651
K3	4,0000
K4	3,7496
K5	4,7334
K6	4,4122
K7	3,0000
K8	4,4122
K9	3,0000
K10	2,4774

According to Table 4 composite that was manufactured from jute has remarkably greater odour results than other single-fibre composites. The best result has been provided by felt composite which was manufactured from cotton, among other single-fibre composites. When double-fibre composites has been examined, the odour results of composites that are contains jute are greater than other one. The best odour result among triple-fibre composites, K10 has the best odour results. Therewithal, it has been observed that odour results are getting greater while jute fibre proportion increase. Felt composite K2 has the best odour results among entire composites in a holistic view. The worst odour result has been provided by K5. The phenolic resin that was used is odourless by its own chemical compound, thus resin has not affected the odour results.

3.2. SAC Factor

The results of impedance tube test been carried out according to ISO 10534-2 standard has been shared in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Impedance tube test results according to ISO 10534-2 standard

The SAC values of felt composites has increased through the frequency. This is an envisaged situation that existed in natura of felt composites. Table 5 contains average sound absorption behaviour value of composites between 1250 Hz – 6300 Hz interval.

Table 5: Average SA behaviour of felt composites between 1250 Hz – 6300 Hz frequency interval

Felt composite	Average sound absorption behaviour (average SAC)
K1	0,8991
K2	0,9308
K3	0,8329
K4	0,9533
K5	0,9188
K6	0,8549
K7	0,9364
K8	0,9225

K9	0,9971
K10	0,9731

In between 1250 Hz – 6300 Hz frequency interval the most performant sound absorption (SA) behaviour was exhibited by composite K9. Nonetheless, K10 and K4 composites were exhibited remarkable SA behaviour in subjected frequency interval, too. K3 and K6 were exhibited the least performant SA behaviour in subjected frequency interval. Composite K1 was exhibited worse SA behaviour than several other composites through the 1250 Hz – 6300 Hz frequency interval, although its SA behaviour was reached to the other felts towards 6300 Hz frequency. The other felt composites K2, K5, K7, and K8 were exhibited SA behaviour approximately same for each other and averagely good. Therewithal, it has detected that as a single-fibre felt composite K2 were exhibited better SA behaviour than other single-fibre felt composites. On the other hand, it has detected that composites, that are contain jute, are more prone to exhibit less SA behaviour performance.

3.3. Cost Factor

Table 6: Unit costs of raw materials

Raw materials	Cost
Denim fibre	€ 1,18
Cotton fibre	€ 2,14
Jute fibre	€ 2,00
Resin	€ 1,72

In Table 6, the costs of raw material for felt composites has been shared as cost of a certain amount of weight for each raw material. Table 7 provides information about the overall cost of each felt composite that in equal weight.

Table 7: Cost factor assessments, overall costs of felt composites

Felt composite	Overall cost
K1	€ 23,85
K2	€ 37,14
K3	€ 35,09
K4	€ 29,72
K5	€ 28,72
K6	€ 36,15
K7	€ 31,35
K8	€ 31,70
K9	€ 31,92
K10	€ 30,50

3.4. Formability Factor

As it has been mentioned before, formability factor has been determined by resin usage in felt composites. Table 8 provides information about formability factor of felt composites.

Table 8: Formability factor assessments

Felt composite	Formability factor
K1	5,33
K2	2,12
K3	1,59
K4	3,73
K5	3,46
K6	1,86
K7	3,01
K8	2,87
K9	2,92
K10	3,25

3.5. AHP Implementation

Criteria evaluation has been made by two experts in felt chemistry. Experts have been built a consensus about criteria evaluation respect to Saaty scale. Table 9 provides information about experts' evaluation of criteria. According to these evaluation Eigenvector has been formed and shared in Table 10.

Table 9: Pair-wise comparison matrix

Criteria	SAC	Cost	Formability	Odour
SAC	1,00	1,00	2,00	5,00
Cost	1,00	1,00	3,00	4,00
Formability	0,50	0,33	1,00	3,00
Odour	0,20	0,25	0,33	1,00

Table 10: Eigenvector (w)

Criteria	Eigenvector
SAC	0,3645
Cost	0,3847
Formability	0,1757
Odour	0,0751

After forming of the Eigenvector, consistency analysis has been made to verify these evaluations are consistent and Eigenvector is usable as criteria's weights for PROMETHEE. After consistency analysis CR has been calculated as 0,0248. Then Eigenvector values has been used in PROMETHEE as of the CR value has met the academical expectations.

3.6. PROMETHEE Implementation

The main formulation for PROMETHEE has been composed as follows, where "O" represents "odour factor", "SAC" represents "SAC factor", "C"

represents "cost factor", and "F" represents "formability factor":

$$P(O) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } (O) \leq 0,6147 \\ \frac{(O) - (0,6147)}{(2,3408) - (0,6147)}, & \text{if } 0,6147 < (O) \leq 2,34088 \\ 1, & \text{if } (O) > 2,34088 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$P(SAC) = \begin{cases} \frac{(SAC)}{(0,0773)}, & \text{if } (SAC) \leq 0,0773 \\ 1, & \text{if } (SAC) > 0,0773 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$P(C) = \begin{cases} \frac{(C)}{(7,7000)}, & \text{if } (C) \leq 7,7000 \\ 1, & \text{if } (C) > 7,7000 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$P(F) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } (F) \leq 0,4848 \\ \frac{(F) - (0,4848)}{(1,6199) - (0,4848)}, & \text{if } 0,4848 < (F) \leq 1,6199 \\ 1, & \text{if } (F) > 1,6199 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Data has been processed within these formulation and PROMETHEE logic. Then Table 11 has been composed as PROMETHEE I data set, which includes positive (ϕ^+) and negative (ϕ^-) preference flow values, and Figure 2 has been formed that represents PROMETHEE I.

Table 11: positive (ϕ^+) and negative (ϕ^-) preference flow values

Felt composite	ϕ^+	ϕ^-
K1	0,4380	0,3432
K2	0,2410	0,3441
K3	0,1410	0,5412
K4	0,3290	0,1612
K5	0,2875	0,2250
K6	0,1212	0,5546
K7	0,2439	0,1683
K8	0,1928	0,2287
K9	0,4150	0,1188
K10	0,3872	0,1113

Figure 2: PROMETHEE I (partial ranking)

Within the PROMETHEE I results, it can be clearly said that composite K6 is the least favourable felt composite to use as cabin insulator according to these criteria. Therewithal, composites K1, K9, and K10 might be good alternative to use as cabin insulator, because of there are not any felt composites that are dominant to these three composites, according to PROMETHEE I. Nevertheless, it is crucial to consider that PROMETHEE I is a partial ranking, thus it might be insufficient to make a decision. Therefore, complete

ranking must be carried out with PROMETHEE II logic. In Table 12, the net flow score calculations has been carried out. Then Figure 3, the complete ranking PROMETHEE II has been formed and shared.

Table 12: Net flow scores

Figure 3: PROMETHEE II (complete ranking)

Within the results of PROMETHEE II as of ultimate decision that processed by all results, composite K9 has selected as the optimal felt composite according to entire criteria with 0,2962 net flow score, which is greatest score among all others. Therewithal, composite K10 might be considerable alternative for composite K9 with its 0,2758 net flow score. Nevertheless, despite composites K4, K1, K7, and K5 have net flow scores above zero, they are not recommended because of the remarkable difference between their net flow score and optimal felt composite's net flow score. Furthermore, it is strongly recommended to avoid using the composites K8, K2, K3, and K6 as cabin insulator according to subjected criteria because of their below zero net flow scores.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The main aim of this paper is to investigate the essential properties and to determine the optimal one of ten different felt composites which are manufactured to use as cabin insulator and successfully passed the flammability and fogging tests. Initially, odour tests have been carried out for subjected composites within the VDA 270 Variant B standard. For an output of this odour test, it has been put forth that jute fibre affects the odour performance unfavourably. Afterwards, impedance tube test has been carried out to SAC values of composites in between 1250 Hz – 6300 Hz frequency interval, within

the ISO 10534-2 standard. It has been put forth that average SA behaviour is getting better while composite getting more complex. Then costs of the felt composites have been calculated based on raw materials' unit price. Formability factor has been determined by resin usage for unit felt production of each individual composites, according to expert suggestions and sectoral experience. Consequently, whole investigation data has been compiled and processed by integrated AHP-PROMETHEE method to determine the optimal felt composite among these ten composites.

Conclusively in this paper, felt composites has been investigated according to their sectoral expectations. Afterwards, these investigations has been evaluated by integrated AHP-PROMETHEE method and K9, which is triple-fibre composite that was manufactured from high proportion of cotton fibre, has been determined as the optimal felt composite to use as cabin insulator.

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